

Swami Vivekanand's views on Spiritual Love

Paper Id : 20462 Submission Date : 2025-07-06 Acceptance Date : 2025-07-21 Publication Date : 2025-07-25

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DOI:10.5281/zenodo.16738438

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Abstract

Vivekananda, as a true follower of Vedanta philosophy, trusts in identifying the real nature of Atman with God. He believes that God resides in humans as the innermost self, and for this reason, God must be worshipped by helping, needful man. Thus, love for you means love for all. This idea of love incites a human being to lead a peaceful and worthy life in our society. The present paper is an attempt to elucidate how Vivekananda's notion of love will help to transform a human's love into divine love and rouse our inner feelings of universal love and thereby resolve the crisis of the present-day Society.

Keywords

Divinity, Service to Man, Notion of Love, Bhakti Vivekanand, Spirituality and Humanity.

Introduction

Swami Vivekananda, a great Indian saint, thinks that spirituality is a direct experience of divine power, and it discloses the inherent divinity among the people. After getting it each individual actively integrates spiritual practices into his/her daily life. He does not perform it through any rituals but through service to humanity.¹ Spiritual love has been experienced through various points of view not only in India but also in the whole universe. Ancient Greek philosophy upheld four different kinds of love, viz, Eros, Philia, Agape, and Storage. The word eros derives from the Greek God Eros, the son of Aphrodite and the Greek equivalent to the Latin Angel. This type of love is extremely emotional and vanishes very soon. Primarily this kind of love is known as the love of passion. Vivekananda was a true follower of Vedanta philosophy, and therefore trusts in identifying the real nature of Atman with God. He believes that God exists in humans as the intimate, and that is why God must be worshipped by helping man in need. Thus, love for you means love for all. This idea of love motivates a human being to lead a peaceful and worthy life in our society.

Objective of study

The present paper is an attempt to elucidate how Vivekananda's notion of love will help to transform a human's love into divine love and rouse our inner feelings of universal love and thereby resolve the crisis of the present-day Society. The present paper deals with Vivekananda's thought on spirituality and universal love which has been glorified in the Advaita Vedanta Philosophy of oneness.

Review of Literature

The notion of love has been observed variously. We also find the concept of love developed by contemporary Indian Philosophers such as Mahatma Gandhi, and Rabindranath Tagore. Like other great thinkers, Mahatma Gandhi writes occasionally about love for all human beings. For Gandhiji, love is a kind of feeling of oneness, the positive aspect of non-violence, it is also the energy that cleanses one's personal life and uplifts one, and love brings some noble feelings such as sympathy, forgiveness, tolerance, kindness, etc. Gandhiji Says, "Love never claims, it never gives. Love never suffers, never resents, never revenges itself."² Gandhiji does not admit the inequity on grounds of anything; such as caste, colour, creed, sex, religion, etc. To him, all human beings are children of God and thus they have the right to be loved equally. In this regard, he says, "If you want to give a message to the West, it must be the message of love."³ Fundamentally, people can think of this kind of love as the love of passion. It is when someone is attracted to someone and loves them, though it does not forever mean that people feel a sexual urge. This type of love is what can be called love at first sight or it may be expressed as madly in love. It is categorized as erratic, passionate, and possessive love. Agape or universal love is the noble type of altruistic love engaged with nature or God. This is described to be akin to the absolute love that God has for everybody. Such kind of love reveals itself in unselfish acts for the universe. It is that kind of conscious choice of unselfishness for the profit of others. Thus, Agape is the purest form of love. Generally, each person loves one another for a reason. When someone feels a kinship with his or her friends, there may be a reason to love them because of the ways that they are like that individual. This is the type of love where people love without any conditions. Agape love is the one kind of love that is actually free from humanity's errors, that love binds people together fast and provides these rich spiritual blessings. Until we have practiced or experienced Agape, we have not experienced real or comprehensive love. Philia love is considered the extremely widespread kind of love in the Bible since it tries to endorse communal well-being such as love of neighbour, attention, collaboration, commitment, and admiration for near people, and friends, but those people who do not necessarily have a family member.

Philia is based on Aristotle's concept of goodwill. Aristotle thought that people can permit goodwill if they are beneficial, enjoyable, or virtuous. Friendships based on mutual goodwill have faith, dependability, and companionship. This type of friendship is said to experience philia's love for one another. Thus, Philia is mainly like the love of the soul, which is described as the kind of love that God loves for us. In some other clarifications, this is the type of love that fathers or mothers feel for their kids and their kids feel for their parents.⁴ Storage love, for some philosophers such as Lewis, holds that it loves others through affection. It is the furthestmost ordinary and largely gentle form of love. But to think philosophically about love, the only way to begin is to reflect on the problems first raised in Plato's Symposium. In Greek Philosophy, Plato's view of love became more popular, which was known as Platonic love. Platonic love is a type of love that is not erotic. Though it is named after the Greek philosopher Plato, he never used the term himself. Platonic love is inspected in Plato's dialogue, the Symposium, which has as its topic the subject of love, which elucidates the potentials of how the feeling of love began and how it has evolved and defines genuine. Platonic love is inspiring a human being's mind and soul and leading his attention toward spiritual matters. Platonic love as invented by Plato concerns rising through levels of intimacy to wisdom and real beauty from carnal attraction to human bodies to attraction to souls, and ultimately, union with the truth. This is the ancient, philosophical interpretation of love.⁵

Main Text**Spiritual Love and Swami Vivekanand**

Now the question is how to realize oneness feelings not only at personal or individual levels, but also at the level of society, or in the universe at large? How do we spread love? Like a true Vedantic Swamiji has proclaimed, "If man grows only physically and mentally but does not side by side grow also spiritually, he will actually use his strength to exploit others, express himself in violence and war, to harm and destroy others and to harm and destroy even himself. But when he grows spiritually also and manifests his ever-present divine dimension, he becomes, capable to express himself in love and compassion, becomes to radiate humanistic impulses towards not only other human beings but also animals."⁶ The most important insight of Vivekananda's concept of love is that it prevents degradation, divinizes human relationships, and makes life meaningful and worth living. Swamiji has laid the foundation for tolerance all over the world.

Our morality in both individual life and social life is mostly based on fear of social criticism. But Swamiji provided a new principle of morality based on the intrinsic purity and oneness of the Atman.⁷ We should love and serve ourselves because purity is our real nature, our true divine Self or Atman. Similarly, we should love and serve our relatives, neighbors, and everyone because we are all one in the Supreme Spirit known as Brahman. If all of us realize the innate divinity of living beings and the essential spirituality of life while running our society then we can make our society free from the bane of privilege and intolerance, inequality, and injustice, which have plagued our society today. Here is the worth of love to be employed. To quote Swamiji: Love opens the most impossible gates and is the gate to all the secrets of the universe.⁸ Hence, we are hopeful that love and unselfish action will lead us to the realization of the highest good.

Swamiji's prime aim in his quest was to reach the overall welfare of the people and to bring about the perfect progress of spiritual consciousness. From his childhood, he was grieving for the deprived and people in need. From infancy, he recognized that his own pleasure was not the aim of his birth. A man can assert his divine nature through the performance of selfless actions, which is described in the Bhagavadgītā as 'niskāma karma' (action without wish of result). Let us try to realize the concept of unselfishness as shown by Vivekananda. Selfishness is to be taken as mortal qualities and a man adhering to the spiritual qualities is taken to be as immortal qualities. Swamiji describes the world as selfish and God as unselfish. Selfishness being a product of ignorance is very much earthly and unselfishness, the product of knowledge, is the form of God. Selfishness is metaphorized by Vivekananda as an old man. As an old man certainly dies, our selfishness has to be removed from our attitudes. Swamiji claims: "Do not give up the world; live in the world, imbibe its influences as much as you can; but if it be for your own enjoyment's sake – work not at all. Enjoyment should not be the goal. First, kill yourself and then take the whole world as yourself... The old man must die. This old man is the selfish idea that the whole world is made for our enjoyment."⁹ So, we should not give up this world, but to live within it. The feeling of love provokes us to sacrifice all our personal needs, when we can love others, we should work for others without any personal intention. Swamiji's vow is to worship people in "Sivajnāne" , sons of lord shiv. The presence of Brahman in the living beings (jīva) means the presence of God. Swamiji's love of humankind and human worship is correlated to atmatattva or Brahmattattva. In order to realize unity and to save the world from total disaster, I would like to refer to the following of the Vedic tradition: vasudhaiva kutumbakam (the entire world is your relation) and the oneness of the Advaita Vedanta. Today as material ideas

are at the height of their glory and power, we are likely to forget our spiritual nature, through our very dependence on the matter and make us only money-making machines. It creates a stressful lifestyle. The degradation of man has been going quickly and largely by increasing broken homes, immorality, crime, and violence. The other important insight of Vivekananda's concept of love is that it does make the realization of unity. The realization of oneness is the first principle of Vedanta. The novelty of Vivekananda's concept of love is that he gives much impetus to the practical side of life. The vision of the Divine is manifested through practice. Thus, Vivekananda's concept of love is not a hopeful thinking or an emotion present as a mere feeling, but it does something positive to alleviate the sorrow of others. To compare the notion of 'love' with contemporary philosophers, we may find some similarities. In order to bring love into every sphere of civilization Mahatma Gandhi established the concept of Sarvodaya for including the well-being of all, love for all, and the happiness of all. Rabindranath also believes in spiritual humanism. Spiritual humanism is honestly a humanistic approach in which human relationship is worshipped as God. We need no glorious place for meditating on knowing ourselves only, nor do we require any to confront our ego to become a spiritual being; rather spirituality can be reached by feeding poor people, serving the destitute, and loving all human beings. Swami Vivekananda believed that all are God. So, the poor, the illiterate, the ignorant, the afflicted- let these be our God. Tagore and Vivekananda's theory of love provides a lot about spirituality. *Gitanjali* (1910) the Nobel-Prize-winning book by Tagore, is the song- offered to God with all humanitarian zeal and a journey from the finite to the infinite for mortals to immortal.¹⁰ Tagore trusts that man can't realize spirituality by shutting his or her eyes, ears, tongue, and five senses and chanting mantras in front of some ideal but by helping others, doing unselfish works with his fellowmen in this very universe and thus man can get the realization that human body is the temple of living God, so to love man is to love the Almighty and to serve mankind is to serve the Supreme, God. God is not to be found in the temple but with the poorest and the lowliest and the lost. In Tagore's spiritualism, there is no place for selfishness and narrow individualism; we are part of the 'great chain of being', so it is important to realize our relation to the larger part of the world.

Conclusion

Thus we can say that understanding of love teaches tolerance. All the followers of Swamiji's vision, ideals, and highest wisdom with faith and regard have made progress. Swami Vivekananda's conception of love offers great hope for modern people. Following it we can easily overcome our problems. We need him for our survival and our guidance. His notion of love is based on truth, sympathy, and tolerance, which will lead us to our individual and collective progress. Recently NEP 2020 applied for the Indian students. It describes that India is a treasure trove of culture, developed over thousands of years and manifested in the form of arts, works of literature, customs, traditions, linguistic expressions, artifacts, heritage sites, and more. The cultural and natural wealth makes India, "Incredible India". The preservation and promotion of India's cultural wealth must be considered a high priority for the country, as it is truly important for the nation's identity as well as for its economy. And Vivekananda's message of love enriches our cultural soul. For Vivekananda, each soul is destined to be perfect, and every human being, in the end, will reach a state of perfection. As he got a message from Advaita Vedantist Shankaracharya and then established the message of 'Tat-Tam-Asi'¹¹ i.e., there is only One Being, i.e., Brahman. So, Vivekananda's sole influence was his novel idea of universal love which led to scientific spiritualism.

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